

Determination Sex from Sternum Bone of Cadaver Brought to Mortuary of Civil Hospital AhmedabadJiniyas Rajvi¹, Kalpesh Shah²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Kalol, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India²Professor & Head, Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, G.C.S Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:

The determination of sex from skeletal remains is highly significant in forensic medicine, physical anthropometry, and anthropology. Exact sex determination from bones has been a key issue in medico-legal issues, and accuracy is dependent on the type of material available and the methods used. Several earlier studies have shown that the sternum is an essential tool for determining sex in mutilated, fragmented carcasses at an advanced stage of decomposition. The sternum is a bone that is easily retrievable, even from the advanced decomposed corpse and the bundle of bone.

Keyword: Sex determination, Medico-legal Autopsy.

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Introduction

Post-mortem investigations of various skeletal elements provide important data for sex estimation. In cases of advanced destruction of skeletal remains, especially pelvis and craniofacial morphometric studies are frequently used methods. [1-6]

“Article 6 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights” states that everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law [7] Sternum is a bone which is easily retrievable even from the advance decomposed body and also from the bundle of bone so it becomes very important bone for sex determination in the advance stage of decomposition and from mutilated, fragmented bodies. Thus, studies focusing on sternum have provided important information to forensic experts. [8]

It is an established fact that study of anthropometry has accurate results, standards vary according to different races and regions, which is why this study is done, and sternum is selected for anthropometry to set the standards.

A primary component of any skeletal analysis is determining sex and stature and anthropologists frequently must accomplish this task in the face of incomplete or fragmentary skeletons. For this reason, developing primary criteria for determination of sex and stature from various skeletal elements has been a primary research focus in skeletal biology. [9]

Objectives

1. Determination of sex from manubrium.
2. Determination of sex from body of sternum.
3. Determination of sex from combined length of manubrium and body of sternum.
4. Determination of sex 1st and 3rd sternbrae.
5. Determination of sex from sternal index.
6. Determination of sex from width index.

Material and Methods

Material: In the present study 170 medicolegal cases were selected. Study was carried of B.J. Medical College, Civil Hospital Ahmedabad during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017.

The materials for the present study consist of sternum bones obtained from the cadavers brought for the post-mortem examination at Civil Hospital, Ahmedabad after taking necessary consent from the relatives and police.

The study and data analysis was done by using SPSS software and relevant statistical test was applied. In our study, Male & Female variation in relation to length of manubrium was found conclusive.

Sternum showing any pathology, fracture, gross deformity or any missing part and body with unknown age will be excluded from the study.

Method

The present study of 170 cases was conducted at mortuary of B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017.

The materials for the present study consist of sternum bones obtained from the cadavers brought for the post-mortem examination at Civil Hospital, Ahmedabad after taking necessary consent from the relatives and police.

All autopsies of medico-legal cases of both sexes, having age above 17 years were included in the study.

The bodies that were decomposed, charred, mutilated and with physical anomalies affecting the study were excluded from the study.

The information about the age of the deceased was obtained from the nearest relatives and investigating officer and was verified by necessary documents. The age of the deceased was rounded off to full figures. Despite of stringent rules on compulsory birth and death registration, there are many cases which do not have a birth certificate today were being excluded from the study.

For determining the sex; all the required measurements were taken with Baker's Digital Calliper having reading accuracy of 0.01mm/0.0005 inches and with measuring range of 0-300 mm/0-12 inches. A rectangular wooden board was taken; all four borders of the wooden board were thicker than then the rest of the board so that while taking measurements sternum remain in contact with two thicker borders placed at 90 degrees with each other. This will confirm the position of the sternum and it will not move while taking the measurement with calliper. The sternum bone taken for measurement was placed on this board in such a way that the posterior surface of the sternum was in contact with the surface of the board. This was further supported

with the hand at the xiphoid region during the examination. The sternum placed in such a way was practically immovable during the examination. After proper positioning, following measurements were taken by digital calliper.

1. Length of manubrium (M): It is the distance from suprasternal notch to sternal angle in midline.

2. Length of body of sternum (B): It is the distance from sternal angle to the junction of body of sternum to xiphoid process in the midline.

3. Combined length of manubrium and body of sternum (M+B): It is the distance from suprasternal notch to junction of body of sternum to xiphoid process in the midline.

4. Width of manubrium (W): It is the maximum width of the manubrium at middle of its length.

5. Width of the first sternebra at its waist (W1): It is the maximum width of the first segment of body of sternum at middle of its length.

6. Width of the third sternebra at its waist (W3): It is the maximum width of the third segment of body of sternum at middle of its length.

7. Manubrio corpus index (Sternal index) = $M/B \times 100$

8. Relative width index of first and third sternabrae = $W1/W3 \times 100$

Result and Observation

The present study of 170 cases was conducted at mortuary of B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017.

Table 1 shows sex wise distribution of length of manubrium (L1) which suggests that maximum number of cases were falling in the range of 46-50.99 mm. in both sexes i.e. 31% in male and 12% in female.

Figure 1: Photograph Showing the Method of Taking Length of Body of Sternum

Figure 2: photograph showing the method of taking combined length of manubrium and body of sternum

Table 1: Sex Wise Distribution of Length of Manubrium (L1)

Length Of Manubrium (In mm.) (L1) in MM.	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
25-30.99	00(0%)	01(1%)
31-35.99	00(0%)	01(1%)
36-40.99	02(2%)	05(5%)
41-45.99	22(22%)	08(8%)
46-50.99	31(31%)	12(12%)
51-55.99	12(12%)	01(1%)
56-60.99	03(3%)	01(1%)
61-65.99	00(0%)	00(0%)
66-70.99	01(1%)	00(0%)
TOTAL	71(71%)	29(29%)

Table 2: Sex Wise Distribution of Length of Body of Sternum (L2)

Length Of Body Of Sternum (L2) In Mm.	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
61-65.99	00(0%)	04(4%)
66-70.99	00(0%)	04(4%)
71-75.99	01(1%)	08(8%)
76-80.99	02(2%)	06(6%)
81-85.99	10(10%)	07(7%)
86-90.99	18(18%)	00(0%)
91-95.99	15(15%)	00(0%)
96-100.99	09(9%)	00(0%)
101-105.99	07(7%)	00(0%)
106-110.99	08(8%)	00(0%)
111-115	01(1%)	00(0%)
Total	71(%)	29(%)

Table 2 shows sex wise distribution of length of body of sternum (L2) which suggests that maximum number of cases in males were falling in the range of 86-90.99 mm. i.e. 18% of total cases and in females' maximum number of cases were falling in the range of 71-75.99 mm i.e. 8% of total cases.

Table 3: Sex Wise Distribution of Combined Length of Manubrium and Body of Sternum (L1+L2)

Combined Length (L1+L2) In Mm.	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
100-105.99	00(0%)	04(4%)
106-110.99	00(0%)	02(2%)
111-115.99	00(0%)	06(6%)
116-120.99	00(0%)	06(6%)
121-125.99	00(0%)	01(1%)
126-130.99	09(9%)	04(4%)
131-135.99	13(13%)	06(6%)
136-140.99	11(11%)	00(0%)
141-145.99	10(10%)	00(0%)
146-150.99	11(11%)	00(0%)
151-155.99	12(12%)	00(0%)
156-160.99	05(5%)	00(0%)
Total	71(71%)	29(29%)

Table 3 shows sex wise distribution of combined length of manubrium and body of sternum (L1+L2) which suggests that maximum number of cases in males were falling in the range of 131-135.99mm. i.e. 13% of total cases and in females maximum number of cases were falling in the three different

ranges i.e. 111-115.99 mm, 116-120.99 mm, 131-135.99 mm that is 6% of total cases in each range. Minimum length of L1+L2 found in male was 126.27 mm and in female it was 100.31 mm. Maximum length was found in male was 159.40 mm and in female it was 135.85.

Table 4 Sex Wise Distribution of Width of Manubrium (W)

Width of Manubrium (W) In Mm.	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
41-45.99	05(5%)	10(10%)
46-50.99	12(12%)	07(7%)
51-55.99	29(29%)	04(4%)
56-60.99	18(18%)	05(5%)
61-65.99	06(6%)	03(3%)
66-70.99	01(1%)	00(0%)
Total	71(%)	29(%)

Above table 4 shows sex wise distribution of width of manubrium(W) which suggests that maximum number of cases in males were falling in the range of 51-55.99 mm. i.e. 29% of total cases and in females maximum number of cases were falling in

the range of 41-45.99 mm that is 10% of total cases. Minimum width of manubrium found in male was 42.95 mm and in female it was 41.49 mm. Maximum width of manubrium found in male was 66.17 mm and in female it was 64.15 mm.

Table 5: Sex Wise Distribution of Width of First Sternebra (W1)

Width Of First Sternebra (W1) In Mm.	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
15-20.99	03(3%)	10(10%)
21-25.99	32(32%)	12(12%)
26-30.99	29(29%)	05(5%)
31-35.99	06(6%)	01(1%)
36-40.99	01(1%)	01(1%)
Total	71(71%)	29(29%)

Table 5 shows sex wise distribution of width of first sternebra (W1) which suggests that maximum number of cases were falling in the range of 21-25.99 mm. in both sexes i.e. 32% in male and 12% in female. Total number of male cases falling in the

range of 21-30.99 mm were 61 i.e. 85.91 % of total number of male cases, while in female total number of cases falling in the range between 15-25.99 mm were 22 i.e. 75.86 % of total number of female cases.

Table 6: Sex Wise Distribution of Width of Third Sternebra (W3)

Width Of Third Sternebra (W3) In Mm.	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
21-25.99	06(6%)	14(14%)
26-30.99	27(27%)	09(9%)
31-35.99	23(23%)	05(5%)
36-40.99	14(14%)	01(1%)
41-45.99	00(0%)	00(0%)
46-50.99	01(1%)	00(0%)
Total	71(71%)	29(29%)

Above table 6 shows sex wise distribution of width of third sternebra (W3) which suggests that maximum number of cases in males were falling in the range of 26-30.99 mm. i.e. 27 % of total number of cases and in females maximum number of cases were falling in the range of 21-25.99 mm i.e. 14% of total number of cases. Number of female cases. Minimum width of third sternebra found in male was 22.37 mm and in female it was 21.29 mm. Maximum width of third sternebra found in male was 50.55 mm and in female it was 37.25 mm.

Table 7: Sex Wise Distribution of Sternal Index (L1/L2×100)

Width Of Third Sternal Index (L1/L2×100) In	No. Of Cases Male (%)	No. Of Cases Female (%)
35-40.99	04(4%)	01(1%)
41-45.99	08(8%)	00(0%)
46-50.99	25(25%)	03(3%)
51-55.99	13(13%)	04(4%)
56-60.99	11(11%)	07(7%)
61-65.99	07(7%)	08(8%)
66-70.99	01(1%)	04(4%)
71-75.99	02(2%)	01(1%)
76-80.99	00(0%)	01(1%)
Total	71(71%)	29(29%)

Above table 7 shows sex wise distribution of sternal index which suggests that maximum number of cases in males were falling in the range of 46-50.99mm. i.e. 25 % of total number of cases and in females maximum number of cases were falling in

the range of 61-65.99 mm i.e. 8% of total number of cases. Minimum sternal index found in male was 39.33 mm and in female it was 36.70 mm. Maximum sternal index found in male was 73.514 mm and in female it was 80.1718 mm.

Table 8: Sex Wise Distribution of Width Index (W1/W3×100)

Width Of Third Width Index (W1/W3×100) In Mm.	No. of Cases Male (%)	No. of Cases Female (%)
55-60.99	02(2%)	00(0%)
61-65.99	00(0%)	01(1%)
66-70.99	08(8%)	01(1%)
71-75.99	11(11%)	01(1%)
76-80.99	09(9%)	03(3%)
81-85.99	08(8%)	09(9%)
86-90.99	12(12%)	07(7%)
91-95.99	08(8%)	02(2%)
96-100.99	08(8%)	01(1%)
101-105.99	00(0%)	02(2%)
106-110.99	05(5%)	01(1%)
111-115.99	00(0%)	00(0%)
116-120.99	00(0%)	00(0%)
121-125.99	00(0%)	01(1%)
Total	71(71%)	29(29%)

Above table 8 shows sex wise distribution of width index which suggests that maximum number of cases in males were falling in the range of 86-90.99 mm. that is 12% of total number of cases and in females maximum number of cases were falling in

the range of 81-85.99 mm that is 9% of total number of cases. Minimum width index found in male was 57.151 mm and in female it was 61.949 mm. Maximum width index found in male was 110.94 mm and in female it was 121.51 mm.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of the Study Sample

Parameter	MALE			FEMALE		
	Min.	Max.	Mean	Min.	Max.	Mean
Age(years)	17	80	37.94±17.47	17	70	32.37±14.67
Width of manubrium (W)	42.95	66.17	54.24±5.23	41.49	64.15	50.73±7.08
Width of first sternebra (W1)	18.92	36.10	26.68±3.63	16.63	39.42	23.58±4.92
Width of third sternebra (W3)	22.37	50.55	31.91±4.84	21.29	37.25	26.98±4.16
Sternal Index	39.33	73.51	52.39±7.70	36.70	80.17	60.12±8.63
Width Index	57.151	110.94	84.63±12.60	61.94	121.51	87.46±11.62

Table shows 9 descriptive statistics of study sample Mean values of all the parameters in male were higher than female except for two parameters i.e. sterna index and width index.

Discussion: Present study of 170 cases was conducted at B. J. Medical College during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017. With aim to study the sternum bone in determining sex as well as to derive regression equations for estimation of stature for both sexes collectively and for both sexes separately.

Table 10: Comparison of Cases According to Sex Wise Distribution of Width of Manubrium (W)

Width of manubrium (In mm.) (W)	Tailor et al. [10]		Present Study	
	Male (%)	Female (%)	Male (%)	Female
41-44	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	05(5%)	10(10%)
45-48	01(0.86%)	01(0.86%)	04(4%)	05(5%)
49-52	14(12.06%)	15(12.93%)	20(20%)	04(4%)
53-57	20(17.24%)	12(10.34%)	23(23%)	03(3%)
58-61	17(14.65%)	11(9.48%)	13(13%)	06(6%)
62-65	15(12.93%)	00(0%)	05(5%)	01(1%)
66-69	05(4.31%)	01(0.86%)	01(1%)	00(0%)
70-73	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	00(0%)
74-77	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	00(0%)
Total	76	40	71	29

In present study maximum number of male cases (23%) were falling in the range of 53-57mm. which was similar to study of Tailor et al. [10] where maximum cases (17.24%) were falling in same range. In present study maximum number of female cases (10%) were falling in the range of 41-44 mm.

while in study of Tailor et al. [10] maximum number of female cases (12.93%) were falling in the range of 49-52mm.

In present study mean of female cases was 50.73 mm and SD ± 7.08 which was 54.4 mm and SD ± 4.12 in study of Tailor et al. [10]

Table 11: Comparison of Cases According to Sex Wise Distribution of Sternal Index

Sternal Index	Tailor et al. ¹⁰		Present Study	
	Male (%)	Female(5)	Male (%)	Female (%)
36-40	01(0.86%)	02(1.72%)	04(4%)	01(1%)
41-44	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	07(7%)	00(0%)
45-48	11(9.48%)	02(1.72%)	14(14%)	03(3%)
49-52	17(14.65%)	07(6.03%)	16(16%)	00(0%)
53-56	20(17.24%)	03(2.58%)	10(10%)	06(6%)
57-60	07(6.03%)	15(12.93%)	10(10%)	05(5%)
61-64	07(6.03%)	03(2.58%)	05(5%)	04(4%)
65-69	05(4.31%)	06(5.17%)	02(2%)	08(8%)
70-73	03(2.58%)	01(0.865)	03(3%)	01(1%)

74-77	02(1.72%)	01(0.865)	00(0%)	00(0%)
78-81	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	01(1%)
Total	76	40	71	29

Observations of sex wise distribution of sterna index of present study were compared with the study of Tailor et al. (2008) [10]. In present study maximum numbers of male cases (16%) were falling in the range of 49-52 mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [10].

Maximum numbers of male cases (17.24%) were falling in the range of 53-56 mm. In present study maximum number of female cases (8%) were falling in the range of 65-69 mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [10] maximum number of female cases (12.93%) were falling in the range of 57-60 mm.

Table: 12 Comparison of Overlapping of Cases in Both Sexes with Other Study

Parameter	Dahiphale et al. (2000) [11] (Male-96 , Female-47)				Present Study (Male-71 , Female-29)				
	Sex	Mean	S.D	P	% In Overlapping	Mean	S.D	P	% In Overlapping
L1	M	48.458	5.586	<0.001	94.79	48.60	4.97	.000	94.36
	F	43.781	5.238		93.61	44.41	5.89		79.31
L2	M	94.427	9.521	<0.001	30.20	93.63	8.35	.000	14.08
	F	70.191	8.541		23.40	74.30	7.16		44.82
L1+L2	M	142.196	11.297	<0.001	61.45	142.24	8.95	.000	30.98
	F	113.872	12.024		42.55	118.71	10.44		34.48
W	M	-	-	-	-	54.24	5.23	.0074	98.59
	F	-	-		-	50.73	7.08		96.55
W1	M	27.166	3.885	<0.001	98.95	26.68	3.63	.001	100
	F	24.444	4.129		89.36	23.58	4.92		86.20
W3	M	31.947	5.77	<0.01	88.54	31.91	4.84	.000	85.91
	F	28.236	4.719		91.48	26.98	4.16		86.20
S.I	M	51.995	8.34	<0.001	44.79	52.39	7.70	.000	97.18
	F	63.01	8.507		95.74	60.12	8.63		96.55
W.I	M	86.291	12.676	>0.05	96.81	84.63	12.60	.290	100
	F	87.16	12.423		100	87.46	11.62		93.10

Observations of present study for percentage of overlapping of cases in both sexes were compared with the observations of study of Dahiphale et al. (2000) [11].

In present study difference in mean of male and female population was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) for all the parameters except for two parameters i.e. width of manubrium ($p = 0.007$) and sternal index ($p = 0.290$). In study by Dahiphale et al. (2000) [11] for all the parameters difference in mean was found statistically significant except for width index ($p > 0.05$).

In present study minimum overlapping of male and female values were found for two parameters i.e. length of body of sternum and combined length of manubrium and body of sternum. These findings were similar to the findings obtained in study of Dahiphale et al. [11] In both the studies, length of body of sternum(L2) and combined length of manubrium and body of sternum(L1+L2) were found most useful for determination of sex. In present study 100% overlapping seen in male subjects for two parameters i.e. width of first sternebra and width index. In study by Dahiphale et

al. [11] 100% overlapping was seen in female subjects in the parameter of width index. In the South Indian male population, a study to obtain linear regression equation to estimate stature from length of sternum bone was done by R.G. Menezes et al. [12] 31 male sterna were included in his study while in present study 71 male sterna and 29 female sterna formed the study sample. Mean (\pm S. D) age of male subjects of the present study was 37.94 ± 17.47 . This was comparable with the study of R.G. Menezes et al. [12] where mean age of male subjects was $38.94 (\pm 13.96)$. Mean (\pm S. D) age of female subjects of the present study was 32.37 ± 14.67 .

In the present study mean (\pm S. D) stature of the male subjects was 161.35 ± 6.30 cm. This was comparable with study of R.G. Menezes et al. [12] where mean stature for male was 166.47 ± 7.22 cm.

In present study mean value of male cases for length of manubrium (48.60 ± 4.97), length of body of sternum (93.63 ± 8.35), width of manubrium (54.24 ± 5.23), width of first sternebra (28.68 ± 3.63), width of third sternebra (31.91 ± 4.84), sternal index (52.39 ± 7.70), width index (84.63 ± 12.60) was also obtained. Mean value of female cases for length of

manubrium (44.41 ± 5.89), length of body of sternum (74.30 ± 7.16), width of manubrium (50.73 ± 7.08), width of first sternbra (23.58 ± 4.92), width of third sternbra (26.98 ± 4.16), sternal index (60.12 ± 8.63), width index (87.46 ± 11.62) was also obtained.

Summary & Conclusions

Following summary was drawn based on present study: Present study of 170 cases was conducted at B. J. Medical College during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017. With aim to study the sternum bone in determining sex as well as to derive regression equations for estimation of stature for both sexes collectively and for both sexes separately.

- Mean length of body of sternum in males was 93.63 mm with SD of 8.35 while that of females was 74.30 mm with SD of 7.16. Length of body of sternum in both sex had overlapping zone in the range of 74.57-84.49 mm. 85.92% of males had length >84.49mm while 55.18% of female had length <74.57mm.
- Mean combined length of manubrium and body of sternum in males was 142.24 mm with SD of 8.95 while that of females was 118.71 mm with SD of 10.44. Overlapping zone in this observation was 126.27-135.85 mm. 69.02% of males had length >135.85 mm while 65.18% of females had length <126.27 mm.
- Mean width of manubrium in males was 54.24 mm with SD of 5.23 while that of females was 50.73 mm with SD of 7.08. Width of manubrium in both sex had overlapping zone in the range of 42.95-64.15 mm. 1.41% of males had length >64.15 mm while 3.45% of females had length <42.95 mm.
- Mean width of 1st sternbrae in males was 26.68 mm with SD of 3.63 while that of females was 23.58 mm with SD of 4.92. Width of 1st sternbrae in both sex had overlapping zone in the range of 18.92-36.10 mm. Observations of all males were falling in this range while 13.80% of female cases were falling outside this range.
- Mean width of 3rd sternbrae in males was 31.91 mm with SD of 4.84 while that of females was 26.98 mm with SD of 4.16. Width of 3rd sternbrae in both sex had overlapping zone in the range of 22.37-37.25 mm. 14.09% of males had length >37.25 mm while 13.80% of females had length <22.37 mm.
- Mean sternal index in males was 52.39 mm with SD of 7.70 while that of female cases was 60.12 mm with SD of 8.63. Sternal index in both sex had overlapping zone in the range of 39.33-73.51 mm. Observations of all male cases were falling in this range while 6.90% of female cases were falling outside this range.
- Mean width index in males was 84.63 mm with SD of 12.60 while that of female cases was 87.46 mm with SD of 11.62. Width index in

cases of both sex had overlapping zone in the range of 61.94-110.94 mm. 2.82% of males had length <61.94 mm while 3.45% of females had length >110.94 mm.

- Regression equation derived for both sexes collectively was “Stature= $94.228 + 4.474 \times$ (Combined Length of manubrium and body of sternum)”, with Standard Error=3.901cm and strength of association=0.858.
- Regression equation derived for male sex was “Stature= $78.027 + (0.586) \times$ (combined length of manubrium and body of sternum)”, with Standard Error=6.706cm and strength of association=0.832.
- Regression equation derived for female sex was “Stature= $104.07 + (0.395) \times$ (Combined Length of manubrium and body of sternum)”, with Standard Error=10.612cm and strength of association=0.650.

So, it is evident from the above findings that out of all the parameters used in the study for determination of sex, length of body of sternum and combined length of manubrium and body of sternum are reliable. All the other parameters are not reliable for sex determination. It is also evident from above findings that out of all the parameters used in the study for estimation of stature, combined length of manubrium and body of sternum is most reliable.

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